

Research

Effectiveness of dyeing with dye extracted from mango leaves on different fabrics by using various mordants

*Burhan Uddin Banna¹, Rony Mia^{*1,2}, Khaleda Sharmin Tanni¹, Nafisa Sultana¹, Al Mojnun Shamim¹, Rahat Khan Turzo¹, Foyisal Khan Limon¹, Muhammad Tanjil¹*

¹Dept. of Textile Engineering, National Institute of Textile Engineering & Research (NITER), Savar, Dhaka 1350, Bangladesh.

²School of Chemistry & Chemical Engineering, Wuhan Textile University, Wuhan 430073, China.

**Corresponding author*

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Abstract: Nature provide us with many resources containing beautiful colors. Natural dyes are now one of the most important research areas for researchers. In this work, the dye was extracted from mango leaves & it was applied on the dyeing for Silk, Cotton & Polyester. The Extraction medium was set up by continue the change of pH value range from 3 to 12. The maximum relative color strength of the extracted dye liquor was found to be at pH 10. The optimum dye extraction conditions i.e., the temperature, time, and material-to-liquor ratio were found to be 98 °C, 60 min, and 1:10, respectively. Different types of mordant is used for fixation. Because Mordanting gives more effective shade in case of dyeing with natural dyes. Here, silk produce fine shades by using different mordants but gives darker shade by using **ferrous sulphate>alum, alum>tin>tannic acid**. Cotton & Polyester gives average result & lighter shades than silk. but by using **alum>tin** Cotton gives dark shades than other mordants, by using **ferrous sulphate>alum>tin** polyester gives a little bit darker shade than other mordants.

Keywords: Natural Dye, Mango Leaves, Mordanting.

Introduction:

Natural dyes are dyes or colorants derived from plants, invertebrates or minerals [1]. Most natural dyes are vegetable dyes from plant sources like:

- Roots
- berries
- bark
- leaves &

- wood

There also some biological sources such as fungi & lichens. Archaeologists have found evidence of textile dyeing dating back to the Neolithic period. But the essential process of dyeing changed little over time. Nowadays many dyes require the use of chemicals called mordants to bind the dye to the textile fibers [2]. Some mordants use with natural dyes such as:

- tannin
- alum
- vinegar
- ammonia
- urea

There are different sources of natural dyes among them leaves are one of the most interesting sources. [3] There have been many researches about extracting natural dye from leaves. Here we work with mango leaves for natural dye extraction from them & want to research about the effectiveness of this dye on different types of fabric specially on cotton, silk, polyester by using different mordants. [4] However, the use of metallic mordants during natural dyeing often puts a question mark on the eco-friendliness of natural dyes. Only a small amount of these metal salts gets fixed onto the textiles and the rest is discharged as effluent which leads to the contamination of land and water resources. [5] Furthermore, the presence of some of these metal salts in the finished goods exposes the wearer to some harm. [6] [7]

Much study has already been dedicated to developing mordanting agents which are nontoxic and eco-friendly. Some of the approaches which have been explored include use of metal salts which are ecologically safe like alum and iron sulphates, use of natural oil product as mordants has also been reported. [8] Tannins and other natural extracts from plants have also been investigated for mordanting natural dyes. In this work we investigate the possibility of dyeing cotton fabric using two natural dye extracts. One dye extract is supposed to act as a mordant while the other acts as the main coloring material. [9] To achieve this objective, we have extracted green dye from Bitter leave (*Vernonia amygdalina*) and used it as the main natural dye. *Vernonia amygdalina* plant is member of the *Asteraceae* family, is a tropical shrub, 1-3m in height with petiole leaf of about 6mm in diameter, and elliptic in shape. The leaves are dark green colored with a characteristic odor and a bitter taste. This plant occurs naturally along rivers and lakes, in forest margins, woodland and grassland, up to 2000 m altitude. [10] It often occurs in disturbed localities such as abandoned farmland and can be found growing

spontaneously in secondary forest making its readily available for use. Extracts from the leaves of the Mango tree (*Mangifera indica*) with a yellowish color has been used as a mordant.

Materials:

1. Dry mango leaves
2. Silk, cotton (woven, knit), polyester fabrics.

Figure 3.1: chemical structure of mangiferin leaves (1, 3, 6, 7- tetrahydroxyxanthone-c-2-β- D- glucoside)

Mango leaves used for the extraction purpose was collected from NITER campus area, Nayarhat, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Mangiferin as shown in Fig. 3.1 (1, 3, 6, 7- tetrahydroxyxanthone-C-2-β-D-glucoside) was the chemical responsible (Luo et al. 2012) for providing color from mango leaves. Silk, cotton, polyester, other materials & chemicals was collected from NITER Wet processing lab.

Methodology:

Extraction: The leaves were washed thoroughly with water to remove dirt. They were dried under direct sunlight and grinded into very small units with the help of a grinder & hand. The wastages are removed using a fine strainer and finally weight was taken. After drying, crushing, and removing wastages, the weight of dry leaves was found on first time work 36gm, second time work 38gm & last time work weight 35gm. Raw, dried, and crushed leaves are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 3.2.1: Mango leaves, Dry mango leaves, Crushed/grinded mango leaves (from left to right)

The color component was extracted from the leaves in aqueous extraction process. Extraction was carried out with fixed quantity of crushed leaves (36, 38 & 35 gram) under pH values from pH 3 to 12 with a liquor ratio of 1:10 at 98 °C for 60 min to optimize extraction medium. In each process of extraction, the mixture cooled down and finally the dye extracts were filtered with fine filter paper three times to ensure clear dye solution.

Figure 3.2.2: boiling mango leaves in beaker Figure 3.2.3: filtration of dye from boiled mango leaves

The higher the alkalinity of the extraction bath, the greater was the pH drop rate. The drop rate became gradually slower while gradually approaching to more acidic bath from neutral bath. The pH was also measured after 24 h of the filtration process to notice the stability of the extracted bath at acidic pH, and no major noticeable change was reported. Again, the dyes can show resonating form and give different tones with the change in pH because for natural dyes, pH changes very often. Furthermore, silk dyeing is recommended to be carried out in acidic medium as silk is sensitive to alkaline medium of dyeing, but extraction of the mangiferin dyes was optimized at alkaline pH. Therefore, the stability of the dyes after extraction is of importance.

Mordanting:

- Pre-mordanting was carried out on silk fabric using 5 % (on fabric weight) of Ferrous sulphate alum (potassium aluminum sulfate), and tin (stannous chloride) mordants individually and using four different combinations of mordants such as ferrous sulphate alum (2.5 + 2.5 %), ferrous sulfate-alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %), alum-tin (2.5 + 2.5 %), and alum tin tannic acid (2 + 2 + 1 %) at 60 °C for 60 min keeping a material-to-liquor is of 1:30.
- Mordanting was carried out on cotton (knit & woven) fabric using 5 % (on fabric weight) of ferrous sulfate, alum (potassium aluminum sulfate), and tin (stannous chloride) mordants individually and using four different combinations of mordants such as ferrous

sulfate-alum (2.5 + 2.5 %), ferrous sulfate-alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %), alum-tin (2.5 + 2.5 %) at 80°C for 1hr keeping a material-to-liquor ratio of 1:30.

- Polyester was mordanting only with ferrous sulfate-alum (2.5 + 2.5 %), ferrous sulfate-alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %) mordants at 100°C for 60min keeping a material-to-liquor ratio of 1:30.

Figure 3.2.4: Mordanting (example-silk)

Table 3.2.1: Mordant use on silk, cotton & polyester fabric for dyeing

Mordant	Ferrous sulfate-alum (2.5 + 2.5 %)	Ferrous sulfate-alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %)	Alum-tin (2.5 + 2.5 %)	Alum-tin-tannic acid (2 + 2 + 1 %)
Silk	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Cotton (woven, knit)	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	–
Polyester	Sample 1	Sample 2	–	–

Dyeing:

- Silk dyeing:-**
- At the first working time dyeing was carried out on oscillating sample dyeing machine with the optimized dye extract as per standard parameters recommended for silk fabric at 80 °C for 60 min under pH 5, keeping the samples into a conical flask with proper material-to-liquor ratio of 1:30.
- After completing dyeing properly washed out the sample with normal water.
- Then dried the sample.

- four sample give similar shade of color which are treated with different mordant before dyeing

Table 3.2.2: Check the shade for each dyeing sample (silk)

Mordant	ferrous sulfate-alum (2.5 + 2.5 %)	ferrous sulfate-alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %)	alum-tin (2.5 + 2.5 %)	alum-tin-tannic acid (2 + 2 + 1 %)
Sample number	1	2	3	4
Sample				

Dyeing color is good for silk fabric because the silk fiber bond with dyes & mordant which is mainly responsible for better result.

Figure 3.2.5: structure of mangiferin with ferrous sulphate on silk fabric.

The presence of hydroxyl or carbonyl groups in dye structure is capable to form metal complex with the positively charged metals. Dye anions and metal cations have strong attraction towards positively charged amino and negatively charged carboxyl groups of silk, respectively. Hence, they form ionic bonding between dye and fiber, metal and fiber, and

finally dye and metal ions. The dye-metal complex also forms coordinate bonds with the uncharged amine ($-NH_2$) groups of silk as shown in Fig.5. In addition, one molecule of dye can form a bond with one site of fiber molecule while one molecule of mordant can form bonds with two or more molecules of dyes. Therefore, these are some of the different features indicating application of mordants increased the color yield (Bhattacharya and Shah 2000; Temani et al. 2011). Again, ferrous sulfate as a transition metal having coordination number 6 forms a large number of complexes with the dye molecules (Mongkhlorattanasit and Punrattanasin 2012). As a result, when they interact with the silk fiber, some coordination sites remain free, and at that time, amino and carboxylic groups on the fiber can occupy these free sites. Thus, ferrous sulfate can form a ternary complex on one site with the fiber and in another site with the dye (Fig.3.2.5). This strong coordination tendency can enhance interaction between the fiber and the dye (Bhattacharya and Shah 2000). This resulted in higher dye uptake as well as shade change due to mordanting with ferrous sulfate.

□ **Cotton dyeing:**

- Second working time dyeing was carried out on oscillating sample dyeing machine with the optimized dye extract as per standard parameters recommended for cotton fabric at 80 °C for 60 min under pH 5, keeping the samples into a conical flask with proper material-to-liquor ratio of 1:30.
- After completing dyeing properly washed out the sample with normal water.
- Then dried the sample.
- four sample give similar shade of color which are treated with different mordant before dyeing

Table 3.2.3: Check the shade for each dyeing sample (cotton):

Mordant	Ferrous sulfate- alum (2.5 + 2.5 %)	Ferrous sulfate- alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %)	Alum-tin (2.5 + 2.5 %)
Sample number	1	2	3

polyester dyeing:

- Natural dyes are not suitable for polyester dyeing but we tried to dyed it with mango leaves extracted dye.
- This dyeing was also carried out on oscillating sample dyeing machine with the optimized dye extract as per standard parameters recommended for polyester fabric at 80 °C for 60 min under pH 5, keeping the samples into a conical flask with proper material-to-liquor ratio of 1:30.
- Then dried the sample.
- four sample give similar shade of color which are treated with different mordant

Table3.2.4: Check the shade for each dyeing sample (polyester)

Mordant	Ferrous sulfate-alum (2.5 + 2.5 %)	Ferrous sulfate-alum-tin (2 + 2 + 1 %)
Sample number	1	2
Sample		

Result:

4.1 Color fastness to light:

- Method:** ISO 105 B02:2013

- Light:** Xenon arc fading lamp test.
- Working procedure:**
 - Keep the sample as per specimen holder size.
 - Set it on to the machine with appropriate method.
- Temperature:**
 - Actual: 46°C
 - Set: 47°C
- RH%:**
 - Actual: 41%
 - Set: 40%
- Testing time:** 3 hours/180minutes.
- Test Results:

Table 4.1: Rating on grey scale

Rating for silk on grey scale				
Sample number	1	2	3	4
Rating	3-4	4	4-5	3-4
Rating for cotton (woven) on grey scale				
Sample number	1	2	3	
Rating	3-4	3-4	4	
Rating for cotton (knit) on grey scale				
Sample number	1	2	3	
Rating	4	3-4	4	
Rating for polyester on grey scale				
Sample number	1	2		
Rating	3-4	4		

Figure 4.1: Color fastness to light.

4.2 Color fastness to rubbing:

Method: ENISO-105-12

Equipment:

- Crock meter
- Cotton ribbing cotton
- Gray scale
- Stop watch
- Color matching cabinet

Specimen preparation:

- Cut two specimens on the bias, 8"×8" & place the test specimen on the crock meter so it will be rubbed in the bias direction.

□ **Test procedure:**

- Mount a dry, white crock test cloth over the finger section of the crock meter so that it will be rubbed in the bias direction.
- Lower the covered finger, causing the crock test cloth to slide over the colored specimen for 10 complete cycles.
- Remove the specimen & the whit crock test cloth
- Perform a wet crocking test by the same procedure.
- Rate the crock test cloths using the color transference chart.

□ **Test result: Table 4.2:** Test results for Color fastness to rubbing

Color fastness to silk				
Sample number	1	2	3	4
Wet	3	4-5	3-4	4-5
Dry	4	3-4	4	4
Color fastness to cotton				
Sample number	1	2	3	
Wet	3-4	4-5	3-4	
Dry	4	4	3-4	
Color fastness to cotton(knit)				
Sample number	1	2	3	
Wet	4	3-4	4-5	
Dry	4-5	4	4	
Color fastness to polyester				
Sample number	1	2		
Wet	4-5	4-5		
Dry	4	4		

Figure 4.2: Color fastness to rubbing

4.3 Color fastness to Perspiration:

□ **Equipment:**

- Perspiration tester
- Oven, maintained at $37\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature
- Multi-fiber test fabric
- Grey scale
- Color matching chamber
- Acidic & alkaline solution
- Weight

□ **Test procedure:**

- Cut the specimen into 10*4cm size.
- Attached the multi-fiber with the samples by sewing.
- Preparing the acid alkali solution of 100ml
- Then immersed the test sample into the acid + alkali solution for 20 min
- Withdraw the fabric & removed any excess liquor
- Placed the specimen in the perspiration tester
- Load the tester with 10 pounds of pressure

- Then kept it into incubator at 37*c temp for 4hr
- Removed the tester from oven & dried at room temp
- Remove the specimen & test cloth then compare the sample with gray scale.

□ **Test rating:**

Table 4.3: Color fastness to perspiration for silk

sample number	Color Change	Color staining					
		Wool	acrylic	polyester	nylon	cotton	Acetate
1	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4	4-5
2	4-5	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4
3	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4	4	4-5
4	4-5	4	4-5	4	4	4-5	4-5

Table 4.3.1: Color fastness to perspiration for cotton (woven)

sample number	Color change	Color staining					
		Wool	Acrylic	polyester	nylon	cotton	Acetate
1	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	3-4	4-5
2	4-5	4	4	4-5	4-5	4	4
3	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4	3-4	4-5

Table 4.3.2: Color fastness to perspiration for cotton (knitted)

sample number	Color change	Color staining					
		Wool	acrylic	Polyester	nylon	cotton	Acetate
1	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	3-4	4-5
2	4-5	4	4	4-5	4-5	3-4	4
3	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4	4	4-5

Table 4.3.3: Color fastness to perspiration for polyester

Sample number	Color change	Color staining					
		Wool	acrylic	Polyester	nylon	cotton	Acetate
1	4-5	4	4-5	4	4-5	4	4-5
2	4-5	4	4	4	4-5	4-5	4

Figure 4.3.: Color fastness to perspiration

4.4 Color fastness to washing:

- **Test method:(ISO-105-C01)**
 - temperature:40*c
 - time:30min
 - chemicals soap(5gm/l)

❖ Test results:

Table 4.4: Test results for color fastness to washing

Rating for silk				
Simple number	1	2	3	4
Rating	4	4	4	4-5
Rating for cotton(woven)				
Simple number	1	2	3	
Rating	3	3	3-4	
Rating for cotton(knit)				
Simple number	1	2	3	
Rating	3	3	3	

Rating for polyester			
Simple number	1	2	
Rating	2.5	2.5	

Table 4.5: Comparison of fastness due to the use of different mordants

Sample Name	Mordant	Color fastness to light	Color fastness to Rubbing	Color fastness to washing	Color fastness to perspiration	Sample shade
Silk	Ferrous sulphate + Alum	3-4	4	4	4-5	
	Ferrous + Alum+ Tin	4	3-4	4	4-5	
	Alum + Tin	4-5	4	4	4-5	
	Alum + Tin+ Tannic Acid	3-4	4	4-5	4-5	
Cotton(Woven)	Ferrous sulphate + Alum	3-4	4	3	4	
	Ferrous + Alum+ Tin	3-4	4	3	4	
	Alum + Tin	4	3-4	3-4	4	
Cotton(Knit)	Ferrous sulphate	4	4-5	3	4	

	+ Alum					
	Ferrous + Alum+ Tin	3-4	4	3	4	
	Alum + Tin	4	4	3	4	
Polyester	Ferrous sulphate + Alum	3-4	4	2.5	4	
	Ferrous + Alum+ Tin	4	4	2.5	4	

Discussion

The results of washing and light fastness of the dyed fabrics are shown in Table 1 & table 4. Using mordants, the color change ratings were found to be within 3/4 to 5, where a rating of 5 (excellent) was found using tin-CT mordant. The ratings were found to be 4/5 in the case of using alum and alum-tin. So it can be said that the overall ratings of color change were good. As wash fastness is influenced by the rate of diffusion of dye molecules and state of dyes inside the fiber, dyes has a tendency to aggregate inside the fiber. Thus, their molecular size is increased resulting in good wash fastness. In addition, in the case of mordanted samples, complexing with mordant also has the effect of insolubilizing the dye, making it color fast. On the other hand, the color staining ratings were found to be from 4/5 to 5 for all the dyed fabrics, except when ferrous sulfate and its combinations were used as mordant. There were very slight staining observed on to the adjacent wool fiber of the multi-fiber fabric in the case of ferrous sulfate and its combination samples where the ratings were 4 and almost no staining on the other fibers of the multi-fiber fabric. Light fastness as shown in Table 1 was found to be better, and among those, the lowest ratings attained were In the case of metallic mordants, ferrous sulfate mordanted samples dyed

with the mango leaf extracts showed excellent light fastness. This happened due to the formation of a complex with transition metal which protected the chromophore from photolytic degradation. The photons sorbed by the chromophoric group dissipated their energy by resonating within the six- member ring thus formed and, hence, protecting the dyes. Thus, ferrous sulfate can bind with more dye molecules than alum or tin. During exposure to light, the fabrics mordanted with ferrous sulfate, alum, or tin may have the same number of dye molecules destroyed. But as the fabrics mordanted with ferrous sulfate had deeper shades due to bonding with more number of dye molecules, it seemed to fade less compared to the fabric mordanted with alum or tin. It can be said that from the comparison table that silk produce fine shades by using different mordants but gives darker shade by using *ferrous sulphate* > *alum*, *alum* > *tin* > *tanic acid*. Cotton & Polyester gives average result & lighter shades than silk. but by using *alum* > *tin* Cotton gives dark shades than other mordants, by using *ferrous sulphate* > *alum* > *tin* polyester gives a little bit darker shade than other mordants

Conclusion:

This study was planned in search of greener alternative to satisfy the consumers' growing demand of eco-friendly products, and progress has been made with this study in the use of mango leaves extracts. But the extracted dye liquors have shown good pH stability in acidic conditions. It was shown that different fashion hues were obtained on silk fabric from the same dye extract using mordants and their combinations. Again, color yields were found to be influenced by the addition of mordants. Other color values were also found to be influenced due to mordanting. Washing and light fastness properties were found to be from good to excellent in most of the cases. Thus, on the basis of the results, it can be said that mango leaves have good scope for application on silk fabrics & can also make effective result on cotton fabric.

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About the Authors:

BURHAN UDDIN BANNA

He is currently working as a Lecturer (Wet Processing) of Textile Engineering Department at National Institute of Textile Engineering (NITER), Nayarhat, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. He has completed B.Sc. in Textile Engineering degree from NITER under University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. Now, he is perusing the degree M.Sc. in Textile Engineering (Wet Process Engineering) at Bangladesh University of Textiles (BUTEX).

RONY MIA

He is currently working as a lecturer of Textile Engineering (Wet Processing) department at National Institute of Textile Engineering & Research (NITER), Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh. He has completed B.Sc in Textile Engineering from NITER under the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. Now, He has enrolled as a postgraduate student at the School of Chemistry & Chemical Engineering in Wuhan Textile University (WTU), China.

KHALEDA SHARMIN TANNI

She is currently working as a lecturer of Garments & Textile Engineering Department at BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jashore, Bangladesh. She has completed B.Sc in Textile Engineering from National Institute of Textile Engineering & Research under University of Dhaka.

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